

Analysis of Production impact and Logistics management sub-systems of Industry 4.0 for an Enterprise in Assam during covid pandemic 2019-21

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(Arunachal Pradesh) – 791109**Abstract:**

The objective of the present investigation is to realize the effect of implementation of Logistics4.0 sub-systems of Industry4.0 for an Enterprise in Assam. There is a negative gross domestic product (GDP) growth of -7.2 percent in 2020-21 in India because of covid 19 pandemic, frequent prolonged lockdowns, illness of employees, lack of transport and logistics support for inbound and outbound raw materials and finished products. The study is considered to highlight the challenges faced by the MSME's of Assam and as well as their future opportunities by implementing proper advanced technologies and guidance. Micro Small Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) which contributes 40% of production in India and these consist of 96% of total industries, so we can say that MSMEs are the actual backbone of Indian Industries. Modernization is eminent which should be achieved sustainably and economically. To explore the reasons in SMEs in Assam both online and off-line are considered.

In the present study also included to find the reasons and their remedies which are responsible for low production and losses arise due to the restrictions followed for the pandemic. And bound to provide reliable suggestions so that the enterprise can thrive and overcome pandemics like COVID-19 in near future without compromising with production and

distribution. This research considered an improved layout of an enterprise which is incorporated with modern equipment and material handling and logistics.

Keywords: Logistics 4.0, Industry 4.0, MSMEs, Covid-19

Introduction –

The word Logistics has a tactical beginning, and used to be related with the development of troops and their provisions in the combat zone. In any case, as such countless different advancements and phrasings, it went into the business vocabulary steadily and has now become inseparable from the arrangement of exercises going from obtainment of natural substances, to the conveyance of the last cleaned great to the end buyer. The term Supply Chain Management was written in 1982 by Keith Oliver of Booz, Allen, and Hamilton Inc. In any case, the discipline and practice has been in presence for a really long time. The terms Logistics and Supply Chain Management are utilized reciprocally nowadays, yet there is an inconspicuous contrast that exists between the two.

Logistics is worried about the two materials stream and data stream. While the materials stream from the provider to customer, the data streams the alternate way round. It isn't just worried about stock and asset use, client reaction additionally falls under the ambit of Logistics. In straightforward terms, Logistics can be viewed as a connection between the assembling and advertising activities of an organization. The conventional associations used to consider them independently, yet there is an unequivocal worth expansion in incorporating the two because of the reliance and criticism channel between the two.

The degree of coordination needed to limit the general expense for the end purchaser gets harder to accomplish as the quantity of members in a production network increment, as an incredibly effective progression of material and data is needed for advancement.

Logistics cover the accompanying wide utilitarian regions: network plan, transportation and stock administration. Assembling plants, stockrooms, stores and so forth are largely offices which structure key parts in the organization plan. Transportation is the expense and consistency (unwavering quality) needed out of the transportation network decides the sort and method of the development of products and furthermore influences the stock.

1. Basic concepts of Logistics and SCM

Logistics is by and large the point-by-point Logistics association and execution of a perplexing activity. In an overall negotiating prudence, Logistics is the administration of the progression of things between the starting place and the mark of utilization to meet the prerequisites of clients or organizations. The assets oversaw in Logistics might incorporate substantial products like materials, gear, and supplies, just as food and other consumable things. The Logistics of actual things typically includes the reconciliation of data stream, materials dealing with, creation, bundling, stock, transportation, warehousing, and frequently security

1.2 Inventory Planning

Associations need to limit the stock levels because of its practically direct relationship with the expense. However assuming the interest is estimated precisely, there would in a perfect world be no requirement for stock and the products will move consistently from stockrooms to clients. That would have been marvellous, yet it is profound into the best world zone. In reality, the anticipated numbers can just take you up until this point and some stock must be kept up with to satisfy any floods popular; the expense of troubled customers who are not adjusted is frequently immense, and is unfathomable in the most cases. However overloads lead to increment in working capital necessities, protection costs and hindered assets which might have been useful somewhere else.

1.3 Transportation

Transportation fills the need for item development, however, capacity also. Time invested for conveyance implies saved energy for warehousing, and ordinarily the expense to offload and reload shipments can be more prominent than the expense of allowing the products to remain in the transportation vehicles themselves. The sort of transportation utilized by an association is an essential choice (it typically represents around 1/3rd of the complete coordinations cost) in light of the necessary degree of hazard openness, client support profiles, the geographic region covered, and so on Truck shipments set aside more effort for conveyance contrasted with air transport (clients with loosened up turnaround times); is less expensive, however, requires the support of higher stock levels.

1.4 Packaging

The ultimate objectives vary: should either be possible for end customers or for strategic contemplations. The bundling will then, at that point, rely upon the ultimate objective; the structure factor plays the lead job when bundling merchandise for the end customers, while work plays the lead job in bundling for strategic activities.

1.5 Warehousing

It is the back-end working for putting away products. In view of the requirements of the association, it very well may be in-house or re-appropriated.

Essential elements of a distribution center are item development and capacity. Exercises, for example, offloading of the products coming from the providers, the middle bundling (whenever required), and delivery to different objections (retailers or end shoppers) are taken care of in the distribution center. Likewise, they can likewise fill in as a capacity house for giving pinnacle buyer interest to keep away from stock out of things and goes about as a cradle between the

beginning stage (generally producing plant) and finishing point (ponder an ordinary retail outlet). Distinctive appropriation procedures can be embraced by an association dependent on its necessities and foundation set up, in particular:

1.6 Cross-Docking

Depends on insignificant handling at the stockroom even out and work with the consistent association among approaching and active merchandise through innovations, for example, standardized tag scanners, turning out to be progressively significant because of setting up organized correspondence among retailer and makers; best for high-speed products with unsurprising interest designs.

2. Industry4.0-

Industry 4.0 uses the force of interchanges innovation and imaginative creations to help the improvement of the assembling business. It supports producing effectiveness by gathering information shrewdly, settling on the right choices, and executing choices with next to no questions. By utilizing the most development advancements, the techniques of gathering and deciphering information will be simpler. The interoperability working capacity goes about as an interfacing extension to give a dependable assembling climate in Industry 4.0. The key parameters of industry 4.0 policy are depicted in fig.1 as -

Fig.1 Subsystem of Industry4.0

This overall consciousness gives Industry 4.0 the most important aspect of artificial intelligent advanced software and networked sensors can be used to plan, predict, functions. The modern and more sophisticated machines and tools with adjust and control the societal outcome and business models to create another phase of value chain organization and it can be managed throughout the whole cycle of a product. Thus, Industry 4.0 is an advantage to stay competitive in any industry. To create a more dynamic flow of production, optimization of value chain has to be autonomously controlled.

3. MSMEs in North East

The eight North East States which cover 263179 Sq. Km of the region that is 8% of India's all-out region face various basic formative difficulties. The district is portrayed by low per capita pay, low capital arrangement, deficient infrastructural offices, correspondence bottleneck, and topographical separation from the standard. Inferable from the presence of multi-pronged shortfalls, the maximum capacity of the NE area couldn't be tapped. In the current setting, the arising MSME area gives another would like to think not exclusively to the jobless populace of the district yet in addition in bringing generally adjusted development.

According to the most recent registration (Fourth Census) directed (with base reference year 2006-07), wherein the information was gathered till 2009 and results distributed in 2011-12, just as information extricated from Economic Census 2005 led by Central Statistics Office (CSO), the quantities of MSMEs in the North-East Region, remembering Sikkim for the MSME Sector represents a sum of 10.64 lakh MSMEs which is very critical contrasting with different pieces of the country. Assam prevalently called the Gateway to North-East India has the biggest number of MSMEs assessed at 6.62 lakhs, lodging various ventures like tea, farming and partners, sericulture, and the travel industry. Coming next in the rundown is Tripura trailed by Manipur, Meghalaya, and Arunachal Pradesh. The commencement list highlights Nagaland and Sikkim on seventh and eighth situations in the rundown separately; attributable to their topographical segregation from the back stream and correspondence bottleneck. This study is directed to the working of existing MSME's of North East. Here the study will cover the facts which will responsible for minimum production as well as profit suffered by the manufacturing enterprises

of this region. For this purpose we will keep an account of important parameters like Human Force, Machine and equipment used in purpose of transportation or logistics.

- Supply Chain
- Production effected due to pandemic.

WE will look forward to maximizing the uses of non-human based applications or automatic systems for the purpose of logistics. Which will deliver advantages like:

- Undisrupted production.
- Minimize accident.
- Zero error.
- Control market price and minimizing scarcity of commodities.

Minimize use of human force, it tends to less accident, minimum ideal time, minimize cost which is not related to production (i.e. health insurance, pensions, support and bonus amount of human worker.)

The will also directed to account some disadvantages like:

- High equipment cost.
- Careful maintenance and high cost.
- It will arise the question of unemployment.

To establish the validation of the advantages in a way so that it can prevail over the disadvantages. For that case the study has to focus on the production and distribution of a factory before and during pandemic. For attaining the sufficient data field visit is made to some Industries, Production and distribution are taken into account.

Case study -1**Dabur India Ltd. Tejpur, Assam**

Dabur Industry is a paramount plant located in Kachamari, Tezpur. When visited there I was looking for the logistics system they are using. They have advanced Technologies for loading and storing purpose. The factory also suffered the COVID-19 crisis but it had overcome the problems with highly maintained logistics device and trained work force.

In loading/unloading point Pet Bottle, CFB box , cap, etc. are being unloaded which are carrying by means of truck, which is also known as RMPM Store area.

They used Hand Trolley which operate by means of hydraulic system, MTANDT lift , Yale , they also used Higher Stacker and Lower Stacker which are electro mechanical., remote operate shuttle are used to bring in or out the stored material.

They have a proper racking area for storage purpose the can carry load up to 14000 kg, maximum distance between two levels are 1550/1600 mm and maximum level load are 2000/1000/2000 kg.

For Mustard oil and LLP (Light Liquid Petrol) they have tank of 150 kl each, the oil are carried by means of tanker. Here various materials are loaded into trucks by means of flexible conveyer (Mit-Moit conveyer Pvt ltd.) They have a good production

Line of 275 ml Dabur Amla hair oil, its filling and capping is done by a series of interconnected machine which use one supervisor and 6 workers for each shift and it runs for three shifts of eight hours. They also use robots for storing and palletize.

Fig.2 Yearly productin Trend Dabur Factory (Tezpur)

Here we can see that production cases in year 2020-21 is inferior to production cases in year 2019-2020, in 2019-20 it has an production of 22,89,511 cases but in the following year due to Covid-19 pandemic the production cases falls to 20,60,062, which a great difference, as a MNC they can make up to this figure but for MSME it is quite impossible to fill this amount of losses. So, MSME has to be greatly reliable on modern and sophisticated technologies which can only be attain by incorporating with Industry4.0 as well as logistics4.0.

Fig.3 Monthly production Trend Dabur Factory (Tezpur) (2020)

In the above figure we can see that in the month of April production cases are very low due to lockdown which results in shut down of the factory, it also suffered low production cases in the month of August, September, October respectively which indicates that Covid-19 has a significant impression on both raw material supply as well as production of furnished goods.

Fig.4 Production assembly line in Dabur plant, Tezpur

Case study -2

Thakuria Polymake Industries (Guwahati)

Thakuria Polymake Industries is located in Industrial estate, Bamunimaidam, Guwahati. It is functioning for nearly twenty years. Its products are Polythene Sheet, Garbage bag etc. Here production is done in two shifts each of eight hours. The industry has sixteen machines having manpower of forty people to run them. The industry has growing since its establishment. In the Year of 2019-20 it produced nearly 400 tons of polythene sheets having a turnover of Rs.3 cores. But we can see significant change of the above mentioned data in the year of 2020-21, due to lockdown imposed on 23rd march,2020 production became Nil, for nearly three months, workers were given a minimum supported payment, even after relaxation of lockdown the was capable to run on only one shift because it can use only 50% of its workforce. For the period of 2020-21 the production is decreased to 160 tons as well as reduction in turnover. The production is affected due to restriction in human movement and shortage of raw materials. Raw materials are Low-density polyethylene (LDPE) & High Molecular Weight High Density Poly Ethylene (HMHDPE). Raw materials are delivered to machine by the use of human work force. Machineries used in the plant are mixture, Injection melding machine, film extrusion machine, Rolling Machine. It seems that the factory need up to date technologies to overcome its traditional barriers.

Fig.5 Granular plastics and mixing machine.

Fig. 6 Warehouse and Plastic Sheet Extrusion Machine.

Case study -3

Milijuli Plastic Industries, Bamunimaidam Guwahati – Assam

Milijuli plastic industry is runs for nearly for thirty five years with its products like plastic sheet, bags, printing label etc. The factory was established in the year of 1985. This factory is also running on raw materials like Low-density polyethylene (LDPE) & High Molecular Weight High Density Poly Ethylene (HMHDPE). Raw materials are delivered to machine by the use of human work force.

This industry is also suffered backlash during the time of Covid-19 pandemic, it also faced lose due to shortage of manpower as well as insufficient supply of raw materials.

The factory works in a simple layout which is consists of both machinery and material handling equipment.

Fig. 7 Production Line of Milijuli Plastic Industries

Various machines like hopper machine, rolling machine, laser printer, PP Blown Film machine etc. also used.

In the year of 2019-20 the plant has a production of 120 tons materials but in the year of 2020-21 it reduced to 96 tons. The main factor which hampered the production line is the human force, which unavailability during the time of pandemic makes the machine stand still.

Fig. 8 Layout of plastic manufacturing factory

Fig. 9 Plastic Sheet Extrusion Machine

Fig.10 Gazetting Machine

Fig.11Gazetting Machine

Fig.12 Finished Product in
warehouse of Milijuli Plastic Industries.

Case study - 4**S.S Fabrication and Industries, Guwahati – Assam**

S.S.Fabrication and Industries, A.K Deb Road, Manapara, Ghy-25 is an industry which deals with steel, stainless steel products. The industry manufactures various steel products like steel table, steel beds, steel furniture, cupboard, various essential products for daily life use. They bring the raw material (steel) from the steel plant and give them a desirable shape for end products. They use various modern equipments like CNC Lathe, CNC Mill, 3D printer, CNC Routers etc.

The main workforce is human, skilled workers are used to carry out the tasks assigned to each machine. But with the Covid-19 pandemic the factory has suffered with loss and minimum production. When the lockdown is implemented there is a restriction on human movement as well as a reduction in transportation. Carrying of raw material as well as supply of end products became very complicated.

Case study – 5**JMB Brick Industry, Palahguri, Morigaon, Assam**

JMB bricks has a capacity of producing seven rounds bricks per production year, each round consists of seven lakhs bricks. In the year of 2018-19 it produced five rounds of bricks, in the year of 2019-20 production was complete seven rounds but due to the ongoing pandemic the production was reduced to three rounds in the year of 2019-20. Same was happened to concrete bricks and block production.

The factory is running on the combination of both human force and machine force likewise traditional way. When lockdown imposed the factory is stripped off their labour force which

hampered in the production line. So it can only produce 21 lakhs of bricks instead of 49 lakhs. That also encourage to raise the manufacturing cost of each bricks from Rs. 3.90 to Rs. 5.00 which in turns effect the market price.As we can see that there is a subsequent rise in concrete blocks also.

Fig. 13 Brick Kiln and Brick Mould

Fig.14 RT9 Block Making Machine

Conclusions:

Improved Flow chart including Inbound and outbound Logistics:

D1, D2, D3- Distributors.
F1, F2 - Food Manufacturing Factories.

By using this layout we can conclude that the enterprise is able to increase the number of working shift from one to three working shift. By using only one third of skilled worker than it's number of human worker at present. That will help the company to maintain social distancing norms easily and help the production unit to overcome the loss due to COVID-19 pandemic. So we can predict if this systems are in incorporated Five years earlier than its last five years forecast would be like this-

Year	Production (Tonne)	Manufacturing Cost (Per Kg in Rest.)	Turn Over (Rest. In crore)
2016-17	1170	72	10.0
2017-18	1200	75	11.2
2018-19	1245	77	12.0
2019-20	1200	78	11.5
2020-21	800	83	9.0

Table.1 Predicted Production data during 2016 to 2021

In the above table we can see the predicted production and turnover of the company with improvised layout, there is a change in manufacturing cost per kg because with implementing of modern logistical devices factors like setup cost, power uses and skilled worker wages are coming out.

Graph 1: Production Comparison between the layouts

P1- Production with existing layout

P2- Predicted Production with improvised layout

Graph 2: Manufacturing Cost Comparison between the layouts

MC1- Manufacturing Cost with existing layout
MC2- Predicted Manufacturing Cost with improvised layout

Graph 3: Yearly Turn over Comparison between the layouts

T1- Turn over with existing layout
T2- Predicted Turn over with improvised layout
The graphs clearly indicate the changes occurred with improvised layout.

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